

UC1 Guidelines for researchers

Defining Procedures and Services to enforce data provenance for thematic communities and beyond

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Executive summary

Due to data exploration complexity, provenance management is a key component in order to guarantee scientific data discovery, reproducibility and results interpretation. Provenance management should be able to define a set of metadata able to capture the derivation history of any stored data, including the original raw data sources, the intermediate data products and the steps that were applied to produce them.

To enable a well-defined data provenance in the scientific experiments workflow, from data production to data usage, we considered two demonstrators coming from two scientific communities: Materials Science/Nanoscience and Climate Science.

The document is structured as a guide for end-users around these demonstrators.

The overall objective is to give researchers and users coming from the community of Materials Science/Nanoscience and Climate science a fundamental understanding of the services provided by each of them and guidance on their use.

1 Introduction

This document provides practical guidance for researchers on using services and tools designed for the FAIRification of research data in two scientific domains: **Materials Science/Nanoscience** and **Climate Science**.

The aim is to guide researchers on services or tools made available and provide some recommendations on how to manage the **provenance** of data in scientific research experiments.

Two distinct demonstrators are presented, related to the Materials Science/Nanoscience and Climate Science domains, respectively. The description of each demonstrator focuses on two main aspects: the description of services and tools made available and instructions to use them.

In the Materials Science/Nanoscience domain, the demonstrator has the final goal to adapt the **W3C PROV standard** to the provenance procedures so far identified in specific cases within the Istituto Officina dei Materiali (CNR-IOM) of the National Research Council (CNR).

In the Climate Science domain, the **W3C PROV standard** has been considered as a recommended set of specifications for tracking processes and responsibilities as well as describing provenance structures within complex experiments and large workflows on scientific data.

1.1 Purpose of the guidelines

The guidelines have been developed to assist researchers through providing:

- Case studies on provenance management
- Information about services provided
- Guidance on using the services and tools made available for the communities

These guidelines should further act as a set of recommendations on managing the provenance of research workflow experiments.

1.2 Targeted users

The targeted users come from two scientific domains: the Materials Science/Nanoscience and Climate Science domain.

1.3 Structure of the document

The document is organised as follows:

- **Introduction**, that gives an overview of the document including the purpose, aim, target users and structure of the document.
- **Context and background**, that includes an overview of the EOSC-Pillar project, UC1 within the WP6 and provenance management.
- **Materials Science/Nanoscience demonstrator**, containing three sections:
 - a. the description of services and tools developed
 - b. instructions to use these services
 - c. outlook in other domains of Materials Science
- **Climate Science demonstrator**, containing two sections:
 - a. the description of tools and applications developed
 - b. instructions to use the service
- **References**
- **Appendixes** with additional information on the procedures that were implemented.

2 Context and background

2.1 EOSC-Pillar overview

The EOSC-Pillar project aims to support the coordination and harmonisation of national initiatives relevant to EOSC in Europe and investigate the option for them to interfederate at a later stage, help integrating initiatives and data/cloud providers through the development of common policies and tools and facilitate user communities in adopting and using these services and propose new ones born from their scientific domain.

The Work Package 6 (*EOSC in action: Use cases and community-driven pilots*) delivers use cases to analyse different tools and services used for the "FAIRification". Among them, the use case 1 ([*UC1: Defining procedures and services to enforce data provenance for thematic communities and beyond*](#)) aims at elaborating cross-domain, FAIR-oriented procedures and recommendations to enforce data provenance by taking into account needs coming from two scientific domains: Materials Science/Nanoscience and Climate Science.

2.2 Provenance management

Provenance management, which tracks all the processes applied to data, from the origin to the final results, is critical to enable reusability in scientific research experiments. To describe the provenance information, the **W3C Provenance Data Model (PROV-DM)** has been used in the proposed case studies.

Specifically, the [W3C PROV](#) standard (Figure 1) has been considered a recommended family of specifications for tracking processes and responsibilities as well as describing provenance structures within complex experiments and large workflows on scientific data.

Figure 1: The Organization of PROV

PROV-DM is the conceptual data model forming a basis for the W3C PROV family of specifications. It is generic, but flexible enough to be exploited in several domains.

Figure 2: PROV Core Structures

Starting from the W3C PROV specifications, the PROV Core concepts (Figure 2) have been applied in the form of adaptations and extensions on top of the existing scientific data services in order to enhance provenance capabilities, thus addressing FAIR-oriented full provenance management.

3 Materials Science/Nanoscience demonstrator

3.1 Description of services and tools

The services provided are related with the creation of a database to store scientific images metadata and the development of a web service for their visualisation [1]. The STM images presented in the reference dataset were recorded using an Omicron Variable Temperature STM (VT-STM) microscope, over twenty years of research activity, by the Surface sTtructure and Reactivity at the Atomic Scale (STRAS) research group of the CNR-IOM Institute in Trieste.

The main objective of this work was the FAIRification and the creation of a curated dataset [2] to allow researchers to build the provenance of data.

Description of the provided services:

- **STM Metadata Database:** a data service to store scientific images' metadata. It helps the discovery of images on the whole dataset by selecting different metadata values as filters, thus improving the findability and accessibility.
- **STM Metadata Explorer:** an easy-to-use and interactive web service that researchers can use to interact with the STM Metadata Database and explore images metadata through interactive and downloadable plots. The crucial component of this web service is metadata enrichment with information on sample composition, obtained with machine learning techniques. It allows visualisation and download functionalities directly in the web browser.

This service is integrated within **Trieste Advanced Data Services (TriDAS)**, designed to enable advanced data services connected to scientific data resources to help researchers in their work.

3.2 Instructions for use

The services are openly available and there is no need to register and login for using them.

To start, go to Trieste Advance Data Services website (TriDAS), by entering <https://tridas.nffa.eu/> on your browser (Figure 3).

The screenshot shows the TriDAS homepage. At the top left, there is a logo and the text "TriDAS is ready to fly!". Below this, a paragraph explains that TriDAS is designed to enable advanced data services connected to the already stored scientific data resources on the NEP shared storage infrastructure. It lists two categories of services: 1) Data Services developed within specific experimental/computational techniques, and 2) Data Services developed at a more general level to address specific class of scientific data (i.e. images, 3D archives). A paragraph below states that the platform is seamlessly integrated in the NEP data repository, allowing users or proposal user groups to access the services immediately and without any need of data transfer. It will be fully operational at Month 31. Services currently offered by the infrastructure include SEM Explorer and STM Explorer. At the bottom, there are two main service cards. The left card is for SEM Explorer, featuring a scanning electron microscope image and a description: "Explore a scanning electron microscope database with more than 100k images simply selecting the metadata you need. Plots are interactive and downloadable." Below the description is a blue button labeled "SEM database explorer". The right card is for STM Explorer, featuring a 3D surface plot and a description: "Explore a 100K scanning tunneling microscope database simply selecting the metadata you need. Plots are interactive and downloadable." Below the description is a blue button labeled "STM database explorer".

Figure 3: Trieste Advance Data Services website (TriDAS)

Actually, TriDAS hosts three virtual access services: SEM Classifier, SEM Explorer and STM Explorer.

Click on **STM database Explorer** located at the bottom right of the homepage. Here you can interact with the platform and find relevant images using just the selected metadata fields without providing specific information.

Use the right toolbar by selecting one or two metadata from X-axis and Y-axis (Figure 4).

The screenshot shows the 'STM Images Database Explorer' interface. At the top, it says 'Select one or two metadata that are stored into our STM images database. We will perform the queries for you!' and 'Explore data thanks to an interactive plot with the possibility to download it.' Below this, there are two dropdown menus: 'Select X-axis' and 'Select Y-axis', both with 'Please select' as the current selection. A 'Submit' button is located at the bottom right of the form area.

Figure 4: STM Images Database Explorer

If you select a single metadata field from one of the axis, and click on the 'submit' icon, will be displayed a quantiles plot that show the distribution of the images with respect to the values of the field (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Quantiles of XOffset

By hovering on top of plot objects, a pop-up shows information about that object: the number of images and value intervals (Figure 5).

The right toolbar allows the interaction with the plots by moving, zooming in and out, and saving plots as images.

Instead, by selecting two metadata fields and clicking on the 'submit' icon, a scatter plot that shows the number of images for each combination of the two fields will be displayed (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Scatter plot of FieldSize and FieldSize Y

By hovering on top of plot objects, a pop-up will show the information about that object: the number of images and metadata value for each field.

Using the right toolbar, you can interact with the plots by moving, zooming in and out, and saving plots as images.

By clicking on top of an object, you will be redirected to a new page containing a table with metadata fields for each image in that subset (Figure 7).

STM Images List

Show entries Search:

ID [↑]	Date [↑]	Label [↑]	FieldXSizeinnm [↑]	FieldYSizeinnm [↑]	ScanAngle [↑]	GapVoltage [↑]	FeedbackSet [↑]	LoopGain [↑]	ScanSpeed [↑]	XOffset [↑]	YOffset [↑]
44004	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.10	0.30	2.00	2083.330	-964.383000	1046.56000
44007	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.10	1.00	2.00	2500.000	321.293000	906.00500
44009	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.20	1.00	2.00	3125.000	-603.742000	789.66800
44019	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.20	1.00	2.00	3125.000	-920.892000	978.33000
44029	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.10	0.30	2.00	2083.330	-957.883000	1029.06000
44099	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.10	0.50	2.00	2083.330	-913.032000	1087.01000
44106	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.30	1.00	2.00	3125.000	-223.940000	460.24000
44111	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.05	1.00	2.00	2500.000	57.362500	253.82500
44114	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.10	1.00	2.00	2500.000	230.293000	724.50500
44117	2011-12-19	Gr_Ni111	100.0	100.0	0.0	-0.05	1.00	2.00	2500.000	68.112500	349.07500

Showing 1 to 10 of 1,276 entries First Previous **1** 2 3 4 5 ... 128 Next Last

Figure 7: List of STM images

On this page you can select, order, filter, and search images based on their metadata values. The metadata presented for each image (from 2nd column to the last) are those that provide significant information about image characteristics and microscope settings as reported below (Table 1).

Metadata	Description
Date	image acquisition date
FieldXSizeinnm	X dimension in nanometers of the scan size
FieldYSizeinnm	Y dimension in nanometers of the scan size
XOffset	X coordinate of the tip offset in nanometers from the center of the scan axes
YOffset	Y coordinate of the tip offset in nanometers from the center of the scan axes
ScanSpeed	speed measured in nanometers per second of the scan

ScanAngle	rotation angle of the fast scan direction in the XY plane measured in degrees
GapVoltage	bias voltage applied between tip and sample in the constant current scan mode, measured in Volts
LoopGain	integral term of the PID feedback loop controller of the tunneling current
FeedbackSet	setpoint of the tunneling current, measured in nanoamperes
Label	sample material composition

Table 1: STM Explorer metadata table

Moreover, the first, ID column, consists of each image unique identifier in the database.

By clicking on it, the corresponding STM image is rendered and shown in a new page. At the bottom are included two download features:

1. Image plot download (Figure 8)
2. Data files, metadata and provenance information download (Figures 8,9)

Figure 8: Filtered image

44029	File con valori separati da virg...	2 KB	No
44029.par	File PAR	4 KB	No
44029.tb0	File TBO	313 KB	No
44029.tf0	File TFO	313 KB	No
STM-PROV	File JSON	5 KB	No

Figure 9: Data files, metadata and provenance information

4 Climate science demonstrator

Climate research makes use of lots of data coming from the modelling and observational climate communities. In this domain, provenance management plays a key role both for numerical end-to-end simulations at data center level and in the inner data analytics workflows. In addition, due to data exploration complexity, provenance management is key to ensuring scientific data reproducibility and sharing, along with results interpretation and data history tracking.

In such a context, provenance tracking can be addressed at two different levels. The first level refers to the whole end-to-end scientific workflow including a proper reference to input and output datasets via PIDs. The second level provides a focus on some first-level tasks, like those regarding data analytics which can be represented themselves as a workflow of micro-tasks (analytics operators) that may usually be in the order of hundreds or thousands.

The main idea is to navigate the first level provenance to have a complete understanding of the overall high-level end-to-end workflow and then have the opportunity to drill-down into some specific analytics tasks to get more detailed information about their internal workflow in terms of micro-tasks or analytics operators. In such a context we can refer to two-level workflows, as two-level provenance management accordingly.

4.1 Description of tools and applications

The climate demonstrator is mainly aimed at scientific users from the core climate modelling community, who are interested in performing scientific data analysis workflows with a stronger provenance support able to track analytics activity at the level of single operators. More specifically, it aims at contributing to the design of a provenance workflow in the field of climate science by identifying suitable provenance procedures as well as leveraging the use of the W3C PROV standard.

The proposed approach relies on a set of easy-to-use templates and tools that can be used in the context of climate science notebooks. This would enable researchers to provide standards conforming to provenance descriptions for their data products.

To account for an in-depth provenance support within the climate processing services, a second-level provenance management complying with the W3C PROV standard has been also elaborated, thus addressing FAIR principles at a finer granularity.

More specifically, guidelines are provided in the form of documentation and interactive Jupyter notebooks currently hosted on GitLab¹ demonstrating the general approach based on concrete data analysis examples.

In addition, a Python application² was developed allowing users to retrieve the provenance documents related to a specific analytics workflow in several formats, such as XML, JSON, RDF or graphical format. This application exploits the PROV Python library³, an implementation of the W3C PROV Data Model supporting PROV-O (RDF), PROV-XML, PROV-JSON import/export.

4.2 How to use the service

The demonstrator is integrated into the **EOSCPillar4EarthScience**⁴ VRE (Virtual Research Environment), an open, cloud-enabled computing environment deployed on the EOSC-Pillar Gateway, the working environment powered by D4Science Infrastructure and designed to promote the collaboration among people involved in the EOSC-Pillar project tasks.

The virtual research environment provides access to large, heterogeneous and distributed climate data, such as CMIP⁵ (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project) collections and CORDEX⁶ (Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment) datasets from the ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation) [3] data archive.

¹ https://gitlab.dkrz.de/data-infrastructure-services/climate_data_provenance/-/blob/master/notebooks/use_case_provenance.ipynb

² <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-provenance>

³ PROV library: <https://prov.readthedocs.io/en/latest/readme.html>

⁴ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillar4earthscience>

⁵ CMIP: <https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip>.

⁶ CORDEX: <https://cordex.org>

The environment relies on JupyterLab⁷, the next-generation user interface for Project Jupyter, and contains a wide set of pre-configured science modules from the Python ecosystem - and in particular from the PANGEO community⁸ - for running data manipulation, analysis and visualization. It also includes an instance of the Ophidia High-Performance Data Analytics framework [4] to enable parallel, in-memory, server-side data analysis and support complex experiments and large workflows on scientific datasets. In addition, Ophidia comes with a programmatic interface for the framework, called PyOphidia⁹, which is an open source python library allowing a programmable integration of the Ophidia operators into more articulated and shareable Data Science applications.

In a typical scenario, end users run data analytics workflows on a compute facility and produce data outputs (e.g. final products, intermediate results) which are published and shared within the community. Then, they may want to search for some data and retrieve provenance information for a better knowledge of the data lineage and the entire analytics process associated with it.

The demonstrator showcases how scientific users running a data analysis and visualization workflow on some data of interest can get provenance records in the form of a provenance graph in addition to the scientific results. More in detail, the proposed approach demonstrates how to generate and integrate PIDs in provenance records along with the usage of helper tools to generate provenance records (first-level) as part of Jupyter notebooks. Moreover, users can exploit the Ophidia framework¹⁰ and integrate an Ophidia-based analysis into a more articulated data analytics workflow; then, based on the information about the executed analytics operators that are tracked by the Ophidia analytics engine, they can get fine-grained (second-level) provenance information, represented according to the W3C PROV specifications and in particular to the mapping between the W3C PROV and the Ophidia concepts described in Appendix 3.

The example below shows a climate workflow consisting of the following tasks:

⁷ JupyterLab: <https://jupyterlab.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

⁸ <https://repository.eosc-pillar.eu/index.php/s/oLas27XDRwscwww#pdfviewer>

⁹ PyOphidia: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/PyOphidia>

¹⁰ Ophidia: <https://ophidia.cmcc.it>

- Data subsetting over the time dimension;
- Temporal aggregation (e.g. maximum over the time series for each point in the spatial domain) and PID generation;
- Climate index computation (e.g. Tropical Nights, the number of days where the daily minimum temperature is above a reference temperature, e.g. 20°C) through the Ophidia framework;
- PID generation and result visualization.

Figure 11: Example of climate analytics workflow

The analysis relies on some open source Python modules and community-based tools, like CDO¹¹, Xarray¹², Ophidia/PyOphidia, Matplotlib¹³ and Cartopy¹⁴. As a first step, users can analyze the first-level provenance associated with the high-level end-to-end workflow.

Figure 12: First-level provenance information based on W3C PROV specifications

The computation of the Tropical Nights climate index is itself a workflow of several micro-tasks (analytics operators) that can be further inspected and explored. In this regard, users can run the developed Python application using the Ophidia logs made available on the client side to get a provenance tracking at a finer granularity.

¹¹ CDO: <https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/>

¹² Xarray: <https://docs.xarray.dev/en/stable/>

¹³ Matplotlib: <https://matplotlib.org/stable/>

¹⁴ Cartopy: <https://scitools.org.uk/cartopy/docs/latest/>

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Caveat: In the JupyterLab file browser (left sidebar) you see the **workspace folder**. This is a **special folder** corresponding to the overall user workspace that is seamlessly shared across several applications and services. The content of this folder has to be managed with care since it is **not locally available** on the JupyterLab instance you are using. It is recommended to **create local copies of the files** you are willing to work with (i.e. have the files you are working with available in places other than the workspace folder) and then (when your working session is going to be closed) **copy them back into the workspace** thus to make the changes available for future uses. Please **let us know** whenever you face any issues.

Name	Last Modified
299263995621886985641522057630934104_31496.txt	an hour ago
299263995621886985641522057630934104_31498.txt	an hour ago
299263995621886985641522057630934104_31500.txt	an hour ago
299263995621886985641522057630934104_31502.txt	an hour ago

```
[7]: | python W3C-PROV_second-level.py --input Ophidia_logs --output .
The Ophidia logs in the Ophidia_logs directory will be processed
The PROV documents will be stored in /home/jovyan
The following log files will be processed: ['Ophidia_logs/299263995621886985641522057630934104_31498.txt', 'Ophidia_logs/299263995621886985641522057630934104_31500.txt', 'Ophidia_logs/299263995621886985641522057630934104_31502.txt', 'Ophidia_logs/299263995621886985641522057630934104_31496.txt']
https://ophidiablab.cmcc.it/ophidia/13537/1189021 https://ophidiablab.cmcc.it/ophidia/13537/1189022 oph_apply 5001972
https://ophidiablab.cmcc.it/ophidia/13537/1189022 https://ophidiablab.cmcc.it/ophidia/13537/1189023 oph_reduce2 5001974
https://ophidiablab.cmcc.it/ophidia/13537/1189023 /home/fantonio/Tropical_Nights_2090-2100.nc oph_exportnc2 5001976
/public/data/tasmin_day_CMCC-ESM2_ssp585_r1i1p1f1_gn_20900101-21001231.nc https://ophidiablab.cmcc.it/ophidia/13537/1189021 oph_importnc2 5001970
```

Figure 13: Python application integrated into the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE to get second-level provenance information based on W3C PROV specifications

Figure 14: PROV-O graphical illustration of the fine-grained provenance information captured at the second level of the Tropical Nights workflow based on W3C PROV specifications

Figure 15: PROV-JSON and PROV-XML documents related to the second-level provenance information captured for the Tropical Nights workflow

5 References

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6 Appendices

Appendix 1: W3C PROV standard

The PROV Family of Documents defines a data model (PROV-DM) along with the corresponding serializations (i.e., PROV-N as a notation aimed at human consumption, PROV-O as the ontology for mapping the PROV data model to RDF, PROV-XML and PROV-JSON as XML schema and JSON representation for the PROV data model, respectively) and other supporting definitions to enable the interoperable interchange of provenance information in heterogeneous environments such as the Web.

The PROV data model defines the mapping of a core set of concepts to types and relations, as shown in the table below.

PROV Concepts	PROV-DM types or relations	Name
Entity	PROV-DM Types	Entity
Activity		Activity
Agent		Agent
Generation	PROV-DM Relations	WasGeneratedBy
Usage		Used
Communication		WasInformedBy
Derivation		WasDerivedFrom
Attribution		WasAttributedTo
Association		WasAssociatedWith
Delegation		ActedOnBehalfOf

Table 2. Mapping of PROV core concepts to types and relations

An **Entity** is a physical, digital, conceptual, or other kind of thing with some fixed aspects.

An **Activity** is something that occurs over a period of time and acts upon or with entities: it may include consuming, processing, transforming, modifying, relocating, using, or generating entities.

An **Agent** is something that bears some form of responsibility for an activity taking place, for the existence of an entity, or for another agent's activity.

The three primary classes are related through a core set of relations:

Generation: the production of a new entity is completed by an activity;

Usage: an activity starts utilizing an entity;

Communication: the exchange of some unspecified entity by two activities, one activity using some entity generated by the other;

Derivation: the transformation of an entity into another, the update of an entity resulting in a new one, or the construction of a new entity based on a pre-existing entity;

Attribution: the ascribing of an entity to an agent;

Association: the assignment of responsibility to an agent for an activity, indicating that the agent had a role in the activity;

Delegation: the assignment of authority and responsibility to an agent (by itself or by another agent) to carry out a specific activity as a delegate or representative.

A graphical view of the PROV Core Structures is shown in the following figure.

Figure 16: PROV Core Structures

Appendix 2: W3C PROV mapping with STM case study and STM provenance workflow

The following table shows the mapping between the elements of STM case study with W3C PROV concept types and relations.

W3C PROV concepts		STM elements
PROV types	Entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw data Reference dataset Structured & FAIR dataset Filtered image
	Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VT-STM measurements Image selection & retrieval Image labelling process Metadata selection
	Agents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> STRAS research group Data scientist Research user VT-STM microscope Analysis software
	Usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Image selection & retrieval used Raw data Image labelling process used the Reference dataset Metadata selection used the Structured & FAIR dataset
	Derivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reference dataset derived from Raw data Structured and FAIR dataset derived from the Reference dataset Filtered image derived from Structured & FAIR dataset
	Generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw data was generated by VT-STM measurements Reference dataset was generated by Image selection & retrieval Structured & FAIR dataset was generated by Image labelling process Filtered image was generated by Metadata selection
	Attribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw data was attributed to STRAS research group Reference dataset was attributed to STRAS research group and Data scientist

PROV relations		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structured & FAIR dataset was attributed to STRAS research group and Data scientist Filtered image was attributed to Research user
	Association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VT-STM measurements were associated with STRAS research group and VT-STM microscope Image selection & retrieval was associated with Data scientist Image labelling process was associated with STRAS research group and Data scientist Metadata selection was associated with Research user
	Delegation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VT-STM microscope acted on behalf of STRAS research group Analysis software acted on behalf of Data scientist

Table 3: Mapping between W3C PROV and STM concepts

The figure below is a graphical representation of the provenance workflow of STM images based on PROV-DM structures.

Figure 17: Graphical representation of the STM core concepts based on PROV-DM core structures and relations

Appendix 3: Mapping between W3C PROV and Ophidia concepts

The following table shows provenance mapping between W3C PROV and the Ophidia elements.

W3C PROV	ECAS objects
Entities	Climate data in NetCDF format (input) Results file(s) in NetCDF format (output) Ophidia datacube
Activities	Ophidia analytics tasks, also known as operators (import, export, subsetting, data reduction, timeseries analytics, etc.)
Generation	NetCDF file or datacube generated by an Ophidia operator
Usage	NetCDF file or datacube used by an Ophidia operator as input
Derivation	Datacube derived from a NetCDF file (Ophidia <i>import</i> operator) or from another datacube (any other Ophidia operator) NetCDF file derived from a datacube (Ophidia <i>export</i> operator)

Table 4: Mapping between W3C PROV and Ophidia concepts

The entities in an Ophidia analytics workflow are the input climate data and the results files (output), both in NetCDF format, as well as each datacube [5] generated/used internally by an Ophidia operator. The activities can be mapped to the tasks within the analytics workflow, each one related to a specific Ophidia operator. Entities and activities are connected through a generation, usage or derivation relation.

Figure 18: Graphical representation of the Ophidia core concepts based on PROV-DM structures

7. List of abbreviations

CDO	Climate Data Operators
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
PID	Persistent identifier
PROV-DM	PROV Data Model
PROV-N	PROV Notation
PROV-O	PROV Ontology
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
STM	Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy
STRAS	Surface sTructure and Reactivity at the Atomic Scale
TriDAS	Trieste Advanced Data Services
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

VT-STM	Variable Temperature Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

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